

THE EVALUATION OF INDONESIA PARALYMPIC COACHING

Deddy Whinata Kardiyanto¹ⁱ,

Hari Setijono²,

Edy Mintarto³

¹Sebelas Maret University,

Jl. Ir. Sutami No. 36, Surakarta, Indonesia

^{2,3}State University of Surabaya,

Jl. Ketintang Baru XII No. 34, Surabaya, Indonesia

Abstract:

The evaluation is conducted with the aim to get a comprehensive, holistic, and empirical picture of Indonesia Paralympic coaching both strategic and technical level, either off the field and in the field. The method of this research is using descriptive method with survey technique. Assessment and analysis were conducted directly on the context dimensions, inputs, processes and products on Indonesia Paralympic coaching. Instruments used to retrieve data includes: (1) questionnaires for athletes; (2) interviews for trainers; (3) interviews for managers; (4) Observation; and (5) secondary data in the form of documents related to the National Paralympic Committee (NPC). The results of data analysis in general is a combination of all data on each factor and indicator, the condition of development of Indonesia Paralympic: (1) athlete recruitment system has been implemented according to the stages that have been set; (2) trainers and assistant trainers meet the criteria set by Indonesia Paralympic; (3) implementation of the exercises, namely: annual program, monthly program, weekly program, daily program, evaluation program has been implemented by Indonesia Paralympic coach; (4) Centralized consumption meets 74%; of expectations (5) board and lodging meet 84% of expectations ; (6) the carrying capacity of infrastructure and facilities meets 72% of expectations ; (7) the characteristics of the central sports are: a) *Induk Cabang Olahraga* has not been conducted yet, b) regional or central NPC, at the same time, play a role as *Induk Cabang Olahraga*; (8) the main source of funds from the government in accordance with applicable legislation through the allocation of APBN and APBD funds, community assistance and membership fees.

ⁱ Correspondence: email deddykardiyanto@mhs.unesa.ac.id

Keywords: coaching, sports, Paralympic, Indonesia

1. Introduction

Exercise is essentially believed to be a miniature of modern human life that is connected easily to become a global community. This can be said so because in sports activities there are aspects which are related to goals, struggles, cooperation, competition, communication and integration, physical strength and mental endurance, togetherness, responsiveness, decision making, self-expression and sportsmanship. All these aspects are aspects that exist in the human being both individually and socially participating actively in the exercise means training one-self to improve the quality of various aspects to exist in the midst of society to be more dynamic. This is also done by disabled athletes who still can compete in the international forum although they only participate in several branch of sport; table tennis and weight lifting categories that can compete in the world while swimming and athletics categories that can compete in Asia. However, these conditions still do not describe the position of Indonesia as a country that has many achievements in the field of sports.

Before exploring further things about the policy that discusses about fostering and development of disabled sports in Indonesia, it is important to know in advance the legislation product (umbrella law) that has been issued by the Government of Indonesia for the sustainability athletes with disabilities in Indonesia, including: (1) The Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 Year 2005; and (2) Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 16, Number 17 and Number 18 Year 2007. In addition, the government also issued Presidential Regulation Number 15 Year 2016 (amendment of Presidential Regulation No. 22/2010) PRIMA) as a national program of sports performance enhancement that is continuously implemented.

Exercise is an integral part of the nation-building process. The process of good sports coaching will ultimately lead to the national sporting achievements that can be proud of in international forums as well as raising dignity of the nation. Talking about Paralympic is not just talking about sports science and competition rules, but talking about the wider thing in life. When talking about Paralympic exercise, it must have a commitment first to foster respect in ourselves for people with disabilities. Such respect can be realized in a simple way, such as no longer using abusive designations for persons with disabilities.

Disabled sports also have multi-events as well as normal sports have, such as: (1) For Southeast Asia level is called Asean Para Games that takes place and held in conjunction with the implementation of the SEA Games; (2) For the Asian level is called Asian Para Games which are held in conjunction with the hosting of the Asian Games;

(3) For the world level is called Paralympic Games that takes place and held in conjunction with the implementation of the Olympic Games. From the multi-events that is owned by disabled sports, it can be analyzed that the National Paralympic Committee Indonesia (NPC Indonesia) is not just a functional sport that only gets less attention, but it should be the main priority because it concerns on the dignity of the nation.

National Paralympic Committee of Indonesia (NPCI) is an organization for athletes with special disabilities in the territory of Indonesia. NPCI derives from an international organization called the International Paralympic Committee (IPC). National Paralympic Committee (NPC) is a sports organization of achievement for athletes with disabilities in a country. This organization in Indonesia was originally named Yayasan Pembina Olahraga Disacusi (YPOC), it was established in Surakarta on 31 October 1962. Based on the suggestion of the Indonesian National Sports Committee (KONI), the Minister of Youth and Sports, the Minister of Social Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia and related parties, YPOC needs to be upgraded to become a sports organization of disabled people of Indonesia by first changing the status from a foundation into a social organization. In the National Sports Conference (Musornas YPOC VII from 31 October to 1 November 1993 in Yogyakarta, then this organization is then established under the new name that is the Board of Trustees of Sports Disability Indonesia (BPOC) as a continuation of YPOC.

In the National Sports Conference (Musornas) X BPOC on 18-20 November 2008 in Surakarta, on the recommendation of the Minister of Youth and Sports of Indonesia and follow the rules of Paralympic institutions at the international level, the BPOC should be enhanced on its existence and its position that the Central BPOC is National Paralympic Committee (NPC). In the Extraordinary National Sports Meeting held on July 26, 2010 in Surakarta, it is changed from BPOC, which was once changed YPOC, becomes NPC Indonesia.

In 2015 according to the Central KONI Decree number 08 / RA / 2015 dated March 31, 2015 National Paralympic Committee (NPC) which was originally one of the fields in the National Sports Committee of Indonesia (KONI) since the decree was issued for NPC became an institution that foster Paralympic sports in Indonesia. Since the date of stipulation of the Decree, it automatically loses its rights and obligations as a member of KONI from the central level to the regions. But despite coming out of KONI, the government is very concerned about the agency that handles the sport for paralympian. This is evidenced in Indonesia Gold Program (Prima) there is a special field in Paralympic. Based on data in 2011, Indonesia always lags behind in achieving Paralympic sports achievement in Southeast Asia level; it can be seen based on Asean Para Games ranking which is held every two years.

Figure 1: Achievement of Indonesia Paralympic on Asean Para Games

(Source: Analysis of Strengths, Challenges, Opportunities and Strategy of Indonesia Facing Multi-Event (R & D Field of Indonesian NPC) on exposure of APG 2015 Singapore APM)

By knowing the achievement of Paralympian Indonesia, then the government starts to not override sports for the disabled. Based on the above description, it is necessary to prepare Indonesia Paralympian to compete harder and be qualified in international; this research will be focused on the Paralympic sports coaching system in Indonesia.

Given the importance of Paralympic sports coaching systems in support of national sports strength, this evaluation was conducted in the hope that the National Paralympic Committee (NPC) program implementation in subsequent years will be better. Evaluation process is a process through an assessment of an object to determine the standard value of the object to be followed up deeper for the progress of achieving the goal.

This study analyzes how the performance process of Paralympic sports development in Indonesia, using CIPP (Context, Input, Process, Product) model, where this evaluation model is considered suitable because CIPP model design allows researchers to conduct a thorough evaluation of the Paralympic sports coaching program in Indonesia. In addition, the CIPP model is also a comprehensive model and is often applied because of its practicality; the evaluation results of this model in accordance with the needs, which means it can facilitate the provision of relevant information to take policy, improvement on each component of the existing system.

Based on this background, the researcher wanted to reveal what factors were carried out in evaluating the Indonesian Paralympic sports coaching system in creating outstanding athletes, especially at international level such as multi events which is equal to Asean Para Games.

Based on the background, the problems in this study can be formulated as follows: (1) Context dimension, which consists of: a) what is the legal basis of Indonesian Paralympic coaching? b) What is the performance and implementation of Indonesian Paralympic organizations and policies? (2) The input dimension, which consists of: a) what is the recruitment of Indonesian Paralympic athletes? B) What is the recruitment of Indonesian Paralympic trainers? C) How to support the Paralympic facilities and infrastructure of Indonesia? D) How to support Indonesia's Paralympic fund? (3) The process dimension, which consists of: a) what is the process of developmental pattern and guidance of Indonesian Paralympic exercise model? B) How to foster social life of Indonesian Paralympic sports athletes? (4) Product dimensions, which are: How is the achievement of Indonesian Paralympic athlete?

2. Evaluation

Evaluation is a systematic process to determine or make decisions that a program has achieved and to collect information about the operation of something, and then the information is used to determine the right alternative in making decisions. The main function of evaluation in this case is to provide useful information for the decision maker to determine the policy to be taken based on the evaluation that has been done.

Similarly, as stated by Surla (2012), that evaluation research aims to collect metadata to initiate improvement or follow-up of a treatment, "In order to evaluate scientific and research results, it is necessary to collect metadata on these results at the beginning". Added by Rosseau (2012) that "the main purpose of evaluation is the strengths and weaknesses of different indicators" suggests that evaluation serves to highlight the strengths and weaknesses of different indicators. Rousseau continues his revelation with the results of the evaluation may differ according to the indicator used "evaluated for different purposes, and hence the results of such evaluation exercises can be quite different depending on the indicator(s) used".

Various definitions of evaluation can also be obtained from experts such as Daniel Stufflebeam (2014). This states that evaluation as a process of approval such as trust, effectiveness, efficiency, security and honesty. Evaluation gives the public a confirmation of the improving accountability values or something that can be justified.

In the evaluation process, there are various assessment models to facilitate the evaluation performance. Several kinds of evaluation research models according to some experts, at least there are ten kinds of models, (1) Goal oriented evaluation model, developed by Tyler. (2) Goal free evaluation model, developed by Scriven. (3) Formative summative evaluation model, developed by Scriven, (4) Countenance evaluation model, developed by Stake. (5) Responsive evaluation model, developed by

Stake. (6) CSE-UCLA Evaluation Model, which emphasizes the "when" evaluation is performed. (7) CIPP Evaluation Model, developed by Stufflebeam. (8) Discrepancy model, developed by Provus, (9) Kirkpartick model, and logic model (logic model).

From the 10 models, the researchers tried to study more deeply to obtain one evaluation model that fits according to the problem of the study. Based on the characteristics of the evaluation model as described earlier, the CIPP Evaluation Model was chosen to evaluate the program in this study. The advantages of this evaluation can evaluate the program to the stage of product and external factors; short-term, medium, and long-term outcomes. The evaluation model is a simple way to conceptualize the actual steps in the evaluation process. The CIPP model from Stufflebeam (2007) defines evaluation as the process of describing, obtaining and providing useful information for assessing decision making alternatives, providing understanding, defining, explaining and focusing information needed by decision makers.

The CIPP evaluation model can be used to improve the improvement of a program that needs to be implemented. More details Stufflebeam (2014) explains that context evaluation is used to identify the strength of objects such as an institution, or programs that will be used for improvement. While for input, evaluation is related to the basic capital approach that will be used to support the training process. The process is the implementation of the program in accordance with detailed plans and input resources and implementation of process effectiveness observation. Medium product is an achievement of the process that has been implemented that shows the effectiveness of the use of inputs and processes.

3. Method

This kind of research is an evaluation research, which is getting a thorough review of Indonesian Paralympic coaching, the evaluation model used is CIPP evaluation model which consists of: (1) context evaluation, (2) inputs evaluation), (3) process evaluation, (4) evaluation of the results (product evaluation). The four stages of evaluation at CIPP are basically the objectives of the evaluation, which are nothing but components of a program. In other words, the CIPP model is an evaluation model that considers the evaluated program as a system.

Figure 2: Design / Design of CIPP Model Evaluation.

The subject of this research is the National Paralympic Indonesia Board, Athletes and Trainers who are members of Pelatnas National Paralympic Indonesia in preparation for Asean Para Games to IX 2017 in Malaysia.

In collecting data, the researchers used various data collection techniques in the form of interview techniques, questionnaires and document studies. Data collection techniques can be described as follows:

Table 1: Objects, Data Sources and Data Collection Techniques

Research objects	Data source	Collecting data technique
1. Context component a. Organisation and structure of sport policies	Athlete, Coach, NPC manager	Interview, questionnaire, document study
2. Input component a. Talent identification and development system b. Financial support c. Sport participation d. Training facilities	Athlete, Coach, NPC manager	Interview, questionnaire, document study
3. Process components a. Athletic and post athletic career support b. Coaches provision an development system c. Scientific research	Athlete, Coach, NPC manager	Interview, questionnaire, document study
4. Product component a. National and international competition	Athlete, Coach, NPC manager	Interview, questionnaire, document study

The research instrument is a questionnaire designed to assess the implementation of Indonesian Paralympic coaching by way of respondents providing feedback statements on a Likert scale. Respondents determine their level of approval of a statement by selecting one of the available options. Data analysis is done after the data collection and data reduction Aare conducted. Analysis of data obtained through questionnaire conducted by descriptive analysis of respondents' answers and interpret the respondent's explanation.

The conclusions of each item that are not meet with the criteria will be deepened through interviews and continued with qualitative analysis. After data collection, then the next step is to analyze the data. Qualitative data analysis is performed based on the CIPP evaluation component. Evaluation analysis is done through the following steps: 1) data collection in accordance with evaluation components, 2) making data displays and analyzing data by comparing data obtained with predetermined criteria, 3) assessing and 4) making decisions and making recommendations.

Figure 3: Flow Chart of Data Processing Sequence Process

Flow chart processing data from raw to the formulation of recommendations can be summarized as follows: (1) raw data from collected instruments processed in the process of the first stage, namely tabulation; (2) The results of the tabulation process is useful for the three following processes, though they are not sequentially with them, ie data analysis, data presentation, and conclusion; (3) The conclusions are based on material sources from data presentation and tabulation of data; and (4) The final process of making a recommendation, based on the material source of the conclusion.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 Context Evaluation

Table 2: The Result of Context Evaluation

Indicators	Results
Organisation and structure of sport policies	Having a strong legal basis and policies about Paralympic sports Indonesia is very appropriate because the Indonesian Paralympic exercise is based on Law no. 3 of 2005 in the National Sport System and Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 15 of 2015 and the Indonesian Paralympic Sports Policy.
	Paralympic Indonesia has a vision and mission that is quite clear, vision is a very crucial thing for an organization to ensure long-term sustainability and success
	Objectives and targets are quite clear, the goal is the translation of the mission statement, which is something that will be achieved or produced within a predetermined timeframe.

The findings show that Paralympic exercise which already has a strong legal foundation will facilitate the implementation of the field. However, it is basically a government effort to make all parties have a strategic role to improve the achievement of Indonesian sports. This is considered very necessary because the pattern of sports coaching is a shared responsibility.

In the vision of an organization must be included the organization values, aspirations and needs of the future. The characteristics of an effective vision must be imagined, desirable, feasible, focused, flexible, and communicable. From the vision made by NPC Indonesia, it can be concluded that the characteristics of imaginable, desirable and communicable have not been seen in its implementation related to equality and balance for the disabled, therefore it is expected that the improvement of vision leads to the above characteristics. While the mission is the fundamental reason for the existence of an organization, mission statement must be able to determine the needs of what is expected by the organization, so the formulation of the mission is a realization that will make an organization able to produce output that can meet the needs and expectations of stakeholders. The findings above shows that the socialization of vision and mission is still lacking because the clarity of vision and mission is still on the order of the nature of the documentation, not delivered to the managers coaches and athletes, so the managers, trainers and athletes do not know the existence of vision and mission. Socialization to the managers, coaches and athletes is not available yet, it is a strong indication that the vision and mission of Paralympic sports Indonesia is not known by the trainers and athletes; it will surely impact on the achievement of the goals. However, in achieving the vision and mission, trainers and athletes should be

included in formulating the vision and mission so that the achievement of the vision and mission of the program becomes easier.

Goals will guide the formulation of objectives, and activities in order to realize the mission, so that goals must harmonize and clarify the mission and vision, describe the program's outcomes and illustrate the clear direction of an organization. While the objective is a translation of the goals of an organization in the final form and will be achieved or produced in the period of annual, semiannual or monthly. The goals also illustrate the things to be achieved through actions taken to achieve the objectives; therefore, the goals set are expected to focus on the preparation of programs and activities that are specific, detailed, measurable and achievable. From the findings, the goals and objectives of Indonesia's Paralympic sports are quite clear and well documented, but the socialization to the managers, coaches and athletes is still not optimal, this is reflected from the ignorance of the managers, coaches and athletes against the goals and objectives to be achieved, Although it has been documented but socialization details of objectives and targets must be done by the manages to trainers and athletes.

4.2 Input Evaluation

Table 3: Input Evaluation Results

Indicator	Results
Talent identification and development system	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Profile and process of athlete's recruitments in accordance with the criteria determined by Indonesia Paralympic.2. Profile and process of coaches' recruitments in accordance with the criteria determined by Indonesia Paralympic.
Financial support	Indonesia Paralympic funding system has been fullfiled properly.
Sport participation	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The support from government that is <i>kemepora</i> in accordance with the regulation on Paralympic provisions.2. The establishment of good cooperation among stakeholders helps implementations of the programs.
Training facilities	The availability of adequate infrastructures and means for exercising

Based on the findings shows that the athlete already has special requirements on the recruitment of athlete candidates, so the requirements for recruitment refer to the Indonesian Paralympic exercise guidelines in accordance with guidelines of the recruitment path of Indonesian Paralympic sports athletes. In the recruitment process, the main thing to be prepared is the conditions that must be met for the prospective athlete. Another finding, it was revealed that there are athletes who put the proximity

factor with the manager although the process of recruitment has been made through the selection and has also been implemented well.

Based on the findings, it does not have specific requirements yet on recruiting candidates for trainers, but within the Indonesian Paralympic exercise guidelines it is already accommodated, so the requirements for recruitment refer to these guidelines. The findings of this research shows that the recruitment of trainers are conducted through appointment, so it needs a further improvement on the recruitment criteria of trainers in accordance with the sport so that the quality of the trainer is maintained.

In the process of training, the existence of facilities and infrastructure is very important. This study found that the Paralympic sports facilities and infrastructure of Indonesia is sufficient, although in the form of quality, it needs to be improved. The existence of many facilities is assisted by Sebelas Maret University and Surakarta City Government. Another thing is also the need for renewal of tools that have been old / less feasible to be replaced with new ones, as well as make efforts to maintain the tool in a planned and integrated manner as mandated by the National Sports System Act Article 67 Paragraph 1 that the government, local government and community are responsible on the planning, procurement, utilization, maintenance and supervision of sports facilities and infrastructure.

The funding of the Indonesian Paralympic sports program is for indefinite pay (manager fee, honor coach and assistant coach and athlete's allowance), other operational items (match costume and training, match shoes and training and matching and training equipment), material shopping (ATK And others), shopping services (Accommodation and athletes consumption), other travel expenses (coach transport and assistant coach, transport try out). The research finds that although funding reporting has been done by managers, it turns out the accountability process and the rest of the managers, coaches and athletes do not know, therefore the transparency and accountability of the Indonesian Paralympic sports funding fund needs to be improved, as mandated in the Law National Sport System Article 71 Paragraph 1 that management of sports funds is based on the principles of fairness, efficiency, transparency and public accountability.

The task of Kemenpora is to formulate, establish and implement the Indonesian Paralympic sports coaching, develop an annual work plan, facilitate NPC Indonesia, manage the activities of Paralympic sports Indonesia, maintain the sports achievement, provide training facilities and infrastructure including board and lodging. The implementation of facilitated training by the government related to infrastructure and NPC Indonesia through the facilities and resources of the trainers has resulted a good coaching, so that the training process can run well.

4.3 Evaluation Process

Table 4: Results of Evaluation Process

Indicator	Results
Athletic and post athletic career support	The aspects of athletes social life coaching, from the respondents showed that the percentage of the social life support for coaching athletes is 67% (good)
Coaches provision an development system	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The exercises implementation is in accordance with stipulated terms in Indonesia Paralympic.2. The aspects of selecting athletes and coaches from respondents can be explained that model indicators have reached 73% (good)3. Training program in accordance with stipulated terms in Indonesia Paralympic.4. Board and loading achievement aspects are 80%, it means there are still 20% from indicator that hasn't been reached yet.
Scientific research	The proper evaluation and monitoring has not been optimal yet, it doesn't appropriate with the stipulated terms of Indonesia Paralympic.

The existing model of Indonesia Paralympic is acceptable to most athletes and coaches, although there are 27% of respondents which are not suitable. Procedure indicator with 80% achievement (good) means the selection procedure available in Indonesia Paralympic can be accepted by most athletes and trainers, From respondents athletes, selection indicator with achievement 93% (excellent) means the results of selection on the sport Paralympic Indonesia is acceptable for Athletes.

The findings state that the training program is an early stage that must be prepared by the board and trainers to implement the training in accordance with the goals and objectives to be achieved. It starts from the preparation of training programs, training administration, test and competition schedules and try out. The Indonesian Paralympic entrepreneurs have made good arrangements, such as making of absences, training schedules and others, while the coach has made plans in arranging the training program, the test schedule, the try out and the match.

The exercise runs according to schedule carried out in the morning starting at 07:00 to 10:00 pm and afternoon at 15:00 to 17:30 pm. In this process, it is also equipped with an exercise program, so the exercise is tailored to the program that has been prepared even though the program is still not completed yet.

Evaluation process has been done in every training session which aims to make improvements / improvements physical, technical and mental athletes so as to achieve the expected goals. Evaluation is an important part of the training process, because without evaluation it is impossible to know how athletes develop. On the other hand, monitoring which is also an important part of a program in this regard in Indonesian paralympic sports has not been carried out continuously. Revealed monitoring from the

board is very rarely done, this can impact badly on the training process. Monitoring is also an attempt to exercise control and motivation for athletes, as there is some kind of concern from the board to the kerjan as an athlete. Therefore, monitoring should be done in a planned and continuous manner.

Results of data analysis of athlete respondents showed that the percentage of achievement for food aspect was 80% (good), thus need to look for solution for food factor to be paid attention especially related to nutrition requirement, so that energy requirement and supplement for compensation from exercise (adaptation) High exercise and impact on the acceleration of achievement. Achievement for lodging is 80% (good), it means that Paralympian rooms should be upgraded, because comfort at rest is an athlete's requirement. With adequate rest means, the process of adaptation and over compensation effect of the exercise process can run quickly and perfectly.

Still athlete's high hope that has not been fulfilled, this can impact on psychic factors, especially the peace of life in relation to family and community life without worrying with his profession as an athlete, who continue to think that later in the post as welfare athletes are not guaranteed.

4.4 Product Evaluation

The product evaluation is intended to evaluate the achievement and welfare of Paralympians and trainers. Achievements at Southeast Asia, Asia and Paralympic levels are in an upward trend. Indonesia Paralympic won the second rank at the level of Southeast Asia in 2011, and then won the 1st rank in 2013, and in 2015 it won the second rank. At the level of Asia, Indonesia Paralympic won the 21st rank, yet in 2012, it turned out to be 9th rank, and at Paralympic it successfully won the silver medal for table tennis category.

In the product, evaluation related to the welfare of athletes is significantly improved economically. The athletes with disabilities are some who are appointed as civil servants and have businesses that can sustain the lives of their families. Meanwhile, the most prominent thing is the realization of equality which becomes the vision of the NPC Indonesia through the equalization of the bonus between Asean Para Games and the Asean Games athletes in the same venue.

Based on the above findings and discussions, it is found that among the components which have been evaluated, there is a system interconnected with one another. All components of context, inputs, processes, and products are important elements in the implementation of a program. Ideally, the above four components must be good in order to produce an achievement. If one of components is wrong and does not work properly, then it will definitely affect the results to be achieved. Therefore, in

running the program we should pay attention to these four components to be managed, so that the objectives of the program can be achieved.

5. Conclusion

Based on the evaluation done by using context model, input, process and product toward Indonesia Paralympic it can be drawn into conclusions, as follows:

1. Context Evaluation

- a. Indonesia Paralympic has a strong and valid legal force in accordance with the provisions of the applicable Law in Indonesia; Indonesia's Paralympic improves the performance of athletes at the International level, Indonesia's Paralympic becomes the acceleration of the achievement of Indonesian sports achievement.
- b. Indonesia's Paralympic has consistency among the vision, mission and goals of NPC Indonesia on the realization of equality and balance in the pattern of athlete coaching that is achieving at the International level.

2. Input Evaluation

- a. Percentage indicator characteristic of athletes of Paralympic sport by 81%, is very good category. But there are still unfinished shortcomings in the characteristics of Paralympic athletes.
- b. The percentage of achievement for the coach characteristics aspect of 83%, is a one-off category. But there are still unfinished shortcomings in the characteristics of Indonesian Paralympic sports coaches.
- c. Percentage of achievement for organizational characteristic is 86%, is good category. But there is still a shortage in the organizing system in Indonesia's Paralympic sport that needs to be improved.
- d. Percentage of achievement for characteristic aspects of facilities and infrastructure support to Paralympic sport by 80%, is good category. But the factors of training, availability, quantity, availability, and construction of facilities and infrastructure have not been fully compatible with Paralympic Indonesia's sport.
- e. Percentage of achievement for funding characteristic aspect of 75%, is good category. But there is still some funding support that has not been done well in Paralympic sport Indonesia.

3. Process Evaluation

- a. Percentage of achievement for athlete and trainer selection aspect is 79% which means it is a good category. However, the model selection factor,

the selection procedure, and the screening organizer have not been fully in line with the demands of Indonesia Paralympic.

- b. Percentage of achievement for training evaluation aspect is 78% that is in good category. However, evaluation model factors, evaluation timing, administration of training evaluation results, and follow-up evaluation results have not been fully in line with the demands of Indonesia Paralympic.
- c. Percentage of achievement for training and match equipment support aspect is 81% that is in good category. However, the support of training equipment and matches on Indonesia Paralympic has not been done as prescribed in Indonesia Paralympic.
- d. Percentage of achievement for board and loading support aspect is 80% that is in good category. But the achievement for the aspects of consumption, lodging, lighting room has not been fully met according to Indonesia Paralympic.

4. Product Evaluation

- a. Indonesian Paralympic athletes are able to achieve the achievements that are proven through the increase of medals in the Asean Para Games, Asian Games and Paralympic events.
- b. The prosperities of athletes are increased and there are vivid equality among Indonesian Paralympic athletes and non-disabled / normal athletes.

6. Suggestions

Based on the conclusion of the research which has been mentioned above, the researcher suggests things as follows:

1. Refining the unfilled shortcomings of the characteristics of Indonesian Paralympic athletes.
2. Refining the unfinished shortcomings in the characteristics of Indonesian Paralympic trainers.
3. Improving the organizing system on Indonesia Paralympic.
4. Increasing the support of Indonesia Paralympic facilities and infrastructures.
5. Increasing the acceleration of disbursing financial support process for Indonesia Paralympic from the government.
6. Refining the selection models, screening procedures, and screening organizers in accordance with the demands of Indonesian Paralympic.

7. Conducting evaluation, administering the results of exercise evaluation, and follow-up evaluation results in accordance with the demands of Indonesia Paralympic exercise.
8. Improving the facilitation of training and game equipment support.
9. Improving the board and loading support services on Indonesia Paralympic.
10. Forming the central organization of Indonesia Paralympic.
11. Implementing the cadreization of Indonesian Paralympic athletes in accordance with the criteria.

Bibliography

1. Agus Kristiyanto. (2012). *Pembangunan Olahraga untuk Kesejahteraan Rakyat dan Kejayaan Bangsa*. Surakarta: Yuma Pustaka.
2. Alkin, Marvin C, (2011). *Evaluation Essentials*. New York: The Guilford Press, A Division of Guilford Publications, Inc.
3. Alman. (2014.) *Evaluasi Program Indonesia Emas*. Desertasi. Universitas Negeri Jakarta. Jakarta
4. Balyi, Istvan. (2013). *Sport System Building and Long-term Athlete Development in British Columbia*. Canada: Sport Med BC.
5. Baker Joseph et al. (2012). *Talent Identification and Development in Sport*. Routledge Taylor & Friends Group London and New York.
6. Baa, Jossey. *New Directions for evaluation*. A Publishing unit of John Wiley and Sons. No. 89 2011.
7. Belia Méndez Rial, José María Cancela Carral. (2015). *Quality Management of Olympic, Non-Olympic and Paralympic Sport Federations*. *Journal of Sports Research* ISSN(e): 2410-6534/ISSN(p): 2413-8436. *Facultade de Ciencias da Educación e do Deporte*. University of Vigo Campus Pontevedra, Pontevedra, Spain. Journal homepage: <http://www.pakinsight.com>.
8. Bidang Penelitian dan pengembangan KONI Pusat. (2014). *Analisis Kekuatan, Tantangan, Peluang dan strategi Indonesia Menyongsong Multi Ajang*. Komite Olahraga Nasional Indonesia. Jakarta.
9. Carlos Montana Hoyos, Lisa Scharoun. (2014). *Design for paralympians: Exploring roles of graphic and industrial design in promoting awareness of athletes with disabilities*. *The International journal of design in society*. www.designprinciplesandpractices.com. ISSN: 2325-1328.

10. Catherine M. Capio, et al. (2015). Fundamental movement skills training to promote physical activity in children with and without disability: A pilot study. *Journal of Sport and Health Science* 4 (2015) 235e243. www.jshs.org.cn.
11. Coaching athletes with a disability – How to be better coach. (2015). Coaching Association of Canada.
12. Cresswell, J.W. (2010). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Approaches*. Third Edition. CAL: Sage Publication.
13. Darcy, Simon. (2012). Paralympic Legacy Learning from Sydney 2000 to Prepare for Tokyo 2020. *Journal of Nippon Foundation Paralympic Research Group* vol 4.
14. David Carless, Andrew C. Sparkes, Kitrina Douglas, Carlton Cooke. (2014). Disability, inclusive adventurous training and adapted sport: Two soldiers' stories of involvement. Leeds Metropolitan University, Fairfax Hall, Headingley Campus, Leeds LS6 3QS, UK Contents lists available at Science Direct Psychology of Sport and Exercise journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/psychsport.
15. Deborah R. Shapiro, Jeffery J. Martin. (2014). The relationships among sport self-perceptions and social well-being in athletes with physical disabilities. Department of Kinesiology and Health, Georgia State University, Atlanta, GA, USA. Wayne State University, USA. *Disability and Health Journal* 7 (2014) 42e48. www.disabilityandhealthjnl.com.
16. De Bosscher Veerle & Jenniver Wong. (2012). Sport Policy Effectiveness in Disability Sport (SPEDS). A Four Year International Comparative Research project. Vrije Universiteit Brussel.
17. _____ . (2014). Sport policy effectiveness in disability sport (speds). Vrije Universiteit Brussel.
18. Donna de Haan. (2015). Evaluating the experience of the Olympic and Paralympic games in the career histories of elite equestrian athletes. Submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of Doctor of Philosophy of Loughborough University.
19. Emzir. (2010). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif: Analisis Data*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo.
20. Farsi, Mitra & Sharif, Maryam. (2014). Stufflebeam's CIPP Model & Program Theory: A Systematic Review. *International Journal of Language Learning and Applied Linguistic World*. Vol 6 (3), July 2014; 400-406.
21. Forward with purpose a strategic framing document for the Canadian Paralympic. (2014). Canadian Paralympic committee.
22. Gizem Karakas, Cetin Yaman. (2014). The role of family in motivating the children with disabilities to do Sport. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*

- 152 (2014) 426 – 429. A School of Physical Education and Sports, Department of Recreation, Sakarya 54187, Turkey.
23. Harshit Topno, "Evaluation of training and development: An Analysis of Various Models", *Journal of Business and Management* Vol 5 (2) 2012, h. 16-22.
24. Husdarta. (2010). *Psikologi Olahraga*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
25. IPC International Standard for Athlete Evaluation. (2014). International Paralympic Committee.
26. Judith Berzen, Yeshayahu. (2012). Evaluating Performance Progression In Beginner Wheelchair Rugby. *European Journal of Adapted Physical Activity*, 5(1), 53-64. European Federation of Adapted Physical Activity. Israel Sport Center for the Disabled, Israel. Zinam College for Physical Education and Sport Science
27. Joan, S. James, "An Evaluation of the Implementation of Aspects of The Revised Jamaican Primary Science Curriculum and Enactment of Professional Development," *Journal of The University of The West Indies*, Vol 2 (3), 2013, hh.1-2.
28. Joshua Ray Pate. (2012). Exploring a Training Facility for Elite Athletes with Physical Disabilities: The Case of Lakeshore Foundation. Trace: Tennessee Research and Creative Exchange. Doctoral Dissertations Graduate School. University of Tennessee, Knoxville
29. Kemenpora. (2010). *Panduan Penelitian Evaluasi dan Kebijakan Olahraga*. Jakarta: Kemenpora.
30. Komite Olahraga Nasional Indonesia. (2014). *Grand Strategi Pembangunan Olahraga Prestasi Nasional 2014-2024*. PT. Gramedia, Jakarta.
31. _____. (2014). *Rencana Strategis (Renstra) Program Indonesia Emas tahun 2015-2019*. Jakarta.
32. *Kumpulan Perundang-undangan & Dasar Hukum Keolahragaan Nasional*. (2015). Kemenpora & KONI. Jakarta
33. Laura Misener. (2013). Managing disability sport: From athletes with disabilities to inclusive organizational perspectives. Contents lists available at Science Direct. Sport Management Review journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/smr. School of Kinesiology, Western University, 1151 Richmond Street, London, Ontario N6A 5B9, Canada.
34. Legg, David. (2010). *Special Report Canadian Sport for Life for Athlete with a Disability*. Calgary, Alberta: Mount Royal University.
35. Long term athlete development Canadian sport for life. (2009). *Canadian sport my live*.

36. Marvin C. Alkin, *Evaluation Roots Tracing Theorists View and Influences* (California: Sage Publications Inc, 2004), h. 34.
37. Mc Cawley, PF. (2013). *The Logic Model for Program Planning and Evaluation*. Online resources <http://www.uiweb.uidaho.edu/extension/logicModel.pdf>. Diunduh 6 April 2016.
38. Massoumi, Hassan et al. (2013) *Presentation of a Entropy Decision Making Pattern to Develop a Comprehensive External Evaluation Model of Sporting Federations Performance Using Fuzzy approach*. *World Applied Sciences Journal* 22 (12): 1718-1728, 2013
39. M. David Miller, (2013). *Measurement and Assessment in Teaching*, 11th Edition. University of Florida. ISBN13: 9780132689663
40. Nagoor Meera Abdullah, Kwame Ampofo-Boateng, Rozita Abdul Latif, Hisyam Che Mat. (2011). *Coaching Athletes with Disabilities – Guidelines and Principles in Training Methodology*. *Jurnal Media Ilmu Keolahragaan Indonesia*. Volume 1. Edisi 1. Juli 2011. ISSN: 2088-6802. <http://journal.unnes.ac.id>. Universitas Negeri Semarang.
41. Nkwake, Apollo M. (2015). *Credibility, Validity, and Assumptions in Program Evaluation Methodology*. Switzerland: Springer International Publishing AG.
42. *Paralympic New Zealand High Performance Plan 2013-2020*
43. Patel, Namrata N. (2014). *Plyometric Training*. *International Journal Curriculum Research Review*. Vol. 6 Issue. 15. Agustus 2014.
44. Patton M. Q, (2006). *How to Use Qualitative Methods in Evaluation*, London: SAGE Publications.
45. *Peraturan Presiden Republik Indonesia nomor 22 tahun 2010 tentang Program Indonesia Emas (PRIMA)*.
46. *Program Pascasarjana, Unesa*. (2015). *Pedoman Penulisan Tesis dan Disertasi*. Universitas Negeri Surabaya.
47. Radtke, Sabine & Doll-Tepper, Gudrun. (2014). *A Cross-cultural Comparison of talent identification and development in Paralympic Sport*. Freie Universitat-Berlin.
48. Rick Cummings. "What if: The Counterfactual in Evaluation Program". *Evaluation Journal Australasia*. Vol. 6, Spring 2016, h. 6-15.
49. Rousseau, Ronald. (2012). *Journal Evaluation Technical and Practical Issues*. *Library Trends*. Vol. 50. No. 3, Winter 2002, pp. 418-439.
50. SK KONI Pusat nomor 08/RA/2015 tanggal 31 maret tentang pengunduran diri NPC Indonesia menjadi anggota KONI.
51. Stufflebeam, Daniel L., Chris L. S. Coryn. (2014). *Evaluation, Theory, Models, & Application*. San Francisco: Jossey – Bass A Wiley Brand.

52. Sean M. Tweedy, Gavin Williams, John Bourke. (2010). Selecting And Modifying Methods Of Manual Muscle Testing For Classification In Paralympic Sport. *European Journal of Adapted Physical Activity*, 3(2), 7-16. European Federation of Adapted Physical Activity.
53. Shia Ping Kung, Peter Taylor. (2014). The use of public sports facilities by the disabled in England, Sport Industry Research Centre (SIRC). Sheffield Hallam University, A118 Collegiate Hall, Collegiate Crescent, SheffieldS10 2BP, UK Contents lists available at Science Direct. *Sport Management Review*. Journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/smr.
54. Simon Nathan. (2013). Athletics Australia's High Performance. Strategic Plan 2013 – 2016.
55. Sudijono, Anas. (2011). Pengantar Evaluasi Pendidikan. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo (Rajawali Pers).
56. Tangkudung, James. (2012). Paragames Paralympic. Jakarta: UNJ.
57. Undang-Undang RI. No.3. (2005). Sistem Keolahragaan Nasional, Jakarta: Kementrian Negara Pemuda Dan Olahraga Republik Indonesia.
58. Whitehead, Ton L. (2015). Cultural Ecology of Health and Change. Maryland: College Park.
59. www.paralympic.org/indonesia.
60. Yahaya, Azizi. (2012). The using of model CIPP in learning program assessment. International conference on challenge and prospects in teacher education, Concorde hotel Shahala.
61. Zhang, G., Zeller, N., Griffith, R., Metcalf, D., Williams, J., Shea, C., Misulis, K. (2011). Using the Context, Input, Process, and Product Evaluation Model (CIPP) as a Comprehensive Framework to Guide the Planning, Implementation, and Assessment of Service-learning Programs. *Journal of Higher Education Outreach and Engagement*. Vol.15

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Special Education Research shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).